

How the past is shaping the future of life science: the convergence of biology, automation, and AI

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Abstract

Automation has been a transformative force for many industries, including manufacturing and chemistry. While the term traditionally referred to mechanical operations to produce physical objects, the definition has since expanded: 1) it can now mean both physical and/or information automation; and 2) it can now produce physical and/or conceptual outputs. While automation has yet to fully revolutionize life science research, much of which still relies on manual processes, we show that biology automation is the ultimate mixture of the concepts listed above – it involves automation of physical and data processing, and production of physical samples as well as conceptual data outputs.

Here, we explore the history of automation and what it can – and cannot – teach us about the future of automated life science experimentation. We examine the current state of automated biology, its major successes, and the remaining barriers to wider adoption. Unlike in other fields, however, automation is reaching broader integration in life science at a time when both biology and AI are reaching their adolescence. We predict that this novel combination of automation, AI, and life science learning will impact the trajectory of biological research in unprecedented ways.

What is automation and why do we use it?

Automation refers to machines that reduce human intervention in carrying out a physical or mental process. This generally falls into two main categories: **physical automation** and **information automation**.

One of the simplest interpretations of automation is any kind of technology that can reduce human intervention in carrying out a process. In the mid-20th century, automation shifted from systems used to reduce or replace human physical labor to increasingly include automated decision-making that helps to abate and/or completely negates the need for human mental labor (Box 1).

Traditionally, automation has been associated with operations producing tangible goods as their endpoints, often in a manufacturing context. In today's automation, data is often itself considered the product, especially in the biological sciences. This shift was portended as early as 1991 by an engineer at Los

Alamos National Laboratory, who suggested that, "The entire function of the laboratory is to convert raw material (samples) into information (data). As such, a transition must be made from material handling to data handling"¹ (Figure 1). Modern computing power, combined with improvements in robotics and the acceleration of artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities has made "automated collection of data" an essential part of the definition of automation. Indeed, automation in life science is the ultimate mixture of all of these concepts: it involves automation of physical and data processing, and the production of physical samples as well as conceptual data outputs.

Figure 1: The entire function of the laboratory is to convert raw material (samples) into information (data). While this has always been the case, the prominence of data and metadata generation, collection, curation, and sharing has increased in biology with the advent of automated, high-throughput experimentation. The expanding power of deep learning, machine learning (ML), and AI has also made such data – and metadata – creation both more useful and more necessary.

Benefits of Automation

- 1 It increases output and productivity, allowing for better process scaling and labor cost saving compared to manual work
- 2 It augments efficiency, thus improving production costs
- 3 It typically improves process quality through increased accuracy, precision, and consistency
- 4 It may improve workers' quality of life by decreasing physically demanding, stressful, tedious, and dangerous tasks
 - It can, in turn, allow humans to concentrate more on cognitive labor than on physical processes
- 5 In biology labs, automation can allow users to do high-throughput (HTP) experiments more easily, increasing both amount and quality of data, and decreasing labor time per amount of data produced
 - Automated machines in such labs often provide access to "micronized" assays that use much smaller amounts of both samples and materials; this can curb experimental costs and sample loss

Limitations of Automation

- 1 Equipment is expensive for both initial buy-in and maintenance
- 2 Faster production can mean that errors also develop and compound more quickly
- 3 Lab groups and companies may have too many products or protocols to allow for effective automation
- 4 More complex automated processes can be more difficult to troubleshoot
- 5 More efficient automated labs may actually require additional specialized workers to operate and maintain the systems (Bainbridge, 1983)
- 6 Training people and organizations to implement and use automation can be costly both in terms of time and money because automated processes often require experts who are highly-trained in electrical and mechanical engineering, software engineering, and brokering machine-human interactions
- 7 Automation can lead to job losses in some sectors
- 8 Some scientists fear that "There is a danger that automation can inhibit creativity in the experimental design process by limiting the opportunities for changing or tinkering with a protocol... They may also feel less able to begin changing things because they lack the confidence or maybe even the authorisation to open the box and begin modifying what is probably an expensive machine" (Holland and Davies, 2020)

Box 1: Benefits and limitations of automation.

A brief history of biology and its path towards embracing automation

T Experimental biology is a relatively young scientific field, particularly compared to physics and chemistry (Figure 2). Physical science has been experimentally studied at least since the time of the first written human records (see Aristotle and Archimedes), and chemistry as a discipline arguably began with Robert Boyle's work in the mid-1600s. As living creatures interacting with both biotic and abiotic environmental factors, humans have been engaged in biological trial and error "research" throughout our existence. However, most biology research was observational until the 1860s with the work of scientists like Mendel and Pasteur².

The foundations for the fields of microbiology and cell biology were laid in 1665 with Hooke and van Leeuwenhoek's invention of the microscope. However, almost two centuries elapsed before these specialities started to gain traction: the germ theory of disease began its rise with John Snow's abatement of the 1849 London cholera outbreak; the understanding that microbes were alive and did not spontaneously arise from inorganic matter came from Pasteur's experiments in the 1850s and '60s³. Microbiology continued to be primarily devoted to understanding diseases through the work of Robert Koch in the 1870s; Koch was responsible for many of the earliest inventions critical to the field, including oil immersion microscopy, the use of agar to grow microbes in dishes, and single colony bacterial isolation^{3,4}. While Gregor Mendel postulated his genetic "Law of Segregation" and "Law of Independent Assortment" in 1865, the term "genetics" was only created in 1905 or 1906 to describe a new science of heredity⁵. "Classical genetics" began around this time, when Thomas Hunt Morgan and colleagues published a book uniting research on chromosomes with Mendelian ideas about heredity. Genetics, as well as microbiology, would remain within the realms of small-scale experiments, population-level correlations, and observational studies until the mid-20th century. While studies in the 1940's demonstrated that a specific gene could control a biochemical reaction and a single step in a metabolic pathway, it took the discovery of the structure of DNA in 1953 to truly hatch the field of molecular biology⁵⁻⁷. This field experienced another evolutionary leap in 1972 when Paul Berg's team developed recombinant DNA technology that allowed researchers to manipulate DNA and genetically engineer organisms⁸. This ability to gain a deeper understanding, test, and shape interactions could be argued to be the true birth of biology as a discipline, in particular one that requires ever-expanding experimental throughput.

Owing to this history, much of biology automation has been built off of devices for manufacturing and from equipment created for chemistry (Figure 2). The first automated chemistry device may have been the filtrate washing apparatus described by Thaddeus Stevens, MD, in 1875⁹. In the early 1910s, chemists designed the first devices made specifically for laboratory automation, in the forms of an automated grinder to expedite coal sample analysis, and an instrument to measure carbon

dioxide⁹. Chemists leveraged the increasing need for chemical analysis in WWI and in the sugar, paper, and rubber industries post-war to improve upon automated systems, making them increasingly diverse and accessible¹⁰⁻¹²; these devices included automated titrators, first made in the late 1920s, that used photocells to sense color changes at titration end points⁹. Seeing the potential for increasing automation in the industry, meetings of the American Chemical Society began devoting sessions to process automation in the 1920s⁹. The labor shortage during WWII created the need for the (semi-) automation of even more labs and factories doing war research and materials production^{13,14}. This normalized the use of automation in chemistry and related manufacturing sectors, resulting in a rapid rise in the use of automation in these fields after the war. These post-war efforts included more use of electric process control in increasingly complex chromatographs, titrators, and spectrophotometers¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Chemists were also likely the first scientists to use computers in conjunction with automation: the first mention of using an analog computer to model simulations of chemical processes was in 1948 and, in 1952, a refining company combined a mass spectrometer with a digital computer to do molecular analyses⁹.

The advent of molecular biology as a field (both on its own and one to be layered atop microbiology, cell biology, ecology, etc.), brought about an increased need for biology automation (Figure 2). Biology started automating by using and adapting available chemistry equipment; this was possible because both disciplines often rely upon aqueous conditions and reactions. However, biology – molecular biology in particular – relies more on working with tiny sample volumes than does chemistry research. This led to the need for methods of accurately and efficiently dispensing microliter amounts of liquids: it could be argued that biology started to be automated in the early 1960s when the first spring-loaded micropipette was patented and offered for commercial use by Eppendorf⁹. The first ever micropipette had been invented three years earlier by a German scientist²⁰, but biology automation still advanced slowly while molecular biology methods were in their infancy: the adjustable micropipette was not created until 1974²¹, and the multichannel micropipette would only arrive on the scene in 1984²². Biology also often necessitates examining phenomena that require massive amplification steps in which inaccuracies in methods can compound into huge errors. This has resulted in the increasing need for more accurate and reproducible lab techniques. While the "automation" in the Eppendorf pipette resulted from a low-tech mechanical spring, it opened the gates for the next major wave of lab automation for biology, ultimately leading to automated liquid handlers. The Hamilton Company (Reno, NV) introduced its Digital Dilutor in 1971, a motor-driven, semi-automated pipetting system; the Zymark Corporation (Hopkinton, MA) came out in 1982 with a robotic system that included a remote-controlled, motor-driven syringe "hand" to

dispense liquids^{19,23}; and Tecan Systems Inc. (San Jose, CA) debuted its Samplers 500 Series, the “first process-controlled, fully automated pipetting workstations” in 1985²⁴. The first arguably HTP liquid handler was created in 1986 by Beckman Coulter (at the time, called SmithKline Coulter; Brea, CA), with its 1000-tip capacity and programmable robot deck²⁵. TomTec (Hamden, CT) developed the first automatic 96-channel liquid handler in 1990; the first Echo from Labcyte (San Jose, CA; now also part of Beckman Coulter) arrived in 2003, with the ability to quickly transfer droplets without using tips or directly contacting the liquid²⁵; and, that same year, Tecan introduced a modular, robotic liquid handler^{19,24}. While automated liquid handling systems continue to evolve, their fundamental forms are based upon these early inventions.

While automation in biology has also made use of chemistry-inspired devices such as titrators, filters, washers, and extractors, two other major areas of biology automation were created for the needs of biologists alone. DNA amplification and sequencing got their start in 1957 when the first DNA polymerase was identified²⁶. Thomas Brock discovered the bacteria *Thermus aquaticus* in 1969, a species that could survive in environments up to 80°C; the DNA polymerase isolated from

this organism in 1976, Taq polymerase, became one of the bases for PCR (polymerase chain reaction) technology²⁷. In 1983, Kary Mullis, a scientist at the Cetus Corporation (Emeryville, CA) developed a technique to exponentially amplify copies of DNA for ease of study; the resulting PCR technique became one of the the most widely used methods in biology today²⁸. The first PCRs were labor intensive, however, leading Cetus to join with the Perkin Elmer Corporation (Norwalk, CT) in 1985 to create an automated thermal cycler; they added a software cycling controller into the machine’s thermal block in 1987^{29,30}. Perkin-Elmer and Cetus made Taq-based PCR machines and their AmpliTaq DNA Polymerase commercially available in 1987³¹. While PCR machines still require a good deal of human pipetting (sans liquid handling devices) and plate handling, they are arguably the most ubiquitous forms of automation in biology labs today.

Simultaneously, and in conjunction with the rise of PCR was the research of Fred Sanger’s group, who ultimately developed a DNA sequencing method in 1977 that used a DNA polymerase, a primer, and nucleotides³². A lab at the California Institute of Technology developed the first semi-automated DNA sequencing machine in 1986; the group’s leader, Leroy Hood,

then worked with scientists at Applied Biosystems Inc. (ABI; Waltham, MA) to both improve the Sanger sequencing method and to create the first commercially-available, automated DNA sequencer that also acquired and analyzed data on a computer^{33,34}. In 1996, a new DNA sequencing technique, pyrosequencing, was introduced, which measured enzymatic luminescence production in an automated and high-throughput manner³⁵; this allowed for the use of natural nucleotides and let scientists observe sequence results in real time³⁶. These new methods and machines continued to increase in popularity after 454 Life Sciences (Branford, CT; later purchased by Roche; Basel, Switzerland) created their first successful commercial machines in 2005. This marked the start of next-generation sequencing (NGS), characterized by using miniaturized (down to picoliter scale) reactions and automation to run huge numbers of reactions in parallel^{36,37}. Illumina (San Diego, CA) continued to improve upon these automations, creating the HiSeq 2000 machine and software in 2010 that dramatically decreased sequencing costs, and the MiSeq benchtop sequencer in 2011 that both increased speed of sequencing (from days to hours) and had a smaller footprint that made sequencing more accessible to thousands of academics with limited lab space³⁸.

Other biology automation advances are typically less accessible to small academic and industrial labs. Lower levels of automation are cheaper, are typically easier to use, take up less lab space,

and can allow for rapid set-up and troubleshooting³⁹; many labs can access PCR machines, DNA sequencers, and even some automated liquid handling systems for these reasons (Figures 3 and 4). Lower levels of automation may actually be more beneficial in many settings, particularly in academia, which require great protocol flexibility and the rapid generation of pilot data; the relative lack of flexibility in automated processes, combined with the high cost of machines, often precludes their use in labs that prioritize scientific protocol diversity over specialization⁴⁰. Indeed, in situations in which smaller and more varied experiments are often carried out, humans may be able to do many protocols faster than machines^{41,42}. However, larger biotechnology companies and government bioresearch facilities have increasingly embraced higher levels of automation, which include different amounts of system modularity, as well as varying degrees of integration of software and AI to control machines, protocols, and data⁴³; (Figures 3 and 4). Indeed, some of the more specialized – and expensive – automated advances initially came from government labs; for example, the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBNL) created the first automated bacteria colony picker in 1991, a machine that used computer image analysis and robotics to automatically identify and pick colonies from agar and array them into microtiter plates⁴⁴. Other biology automation advances include lab-on-a-chip (LOC) devices, first offered in 1999 by Agilent Technologies

Figure 4: Biology is hard to automate because it exists at the intersection of physical (machines) and information (data and metadata) automation. The more physical automation is used, the more data is produced, and the more information automation is needed. Conversely, the more data that is required to create powerful ML and AI models, the more automation is required to achieve HTP experimentation and large data outputs. The level of automation used for an experiment depends on several factors, including sample characteristics, protocol requirements, knowledge of automation and coding, financial constraints, and laboratory space. Thus, while many biology labs (particularly in academia) currently exist in the lower left portion of this graph, access to the data-machine-automation combination in the green area of the figure is still relatively rare.

(Palo Alto, CA). These devices incorporate several lab methods/ processes onto a tiny (smaller than a few square cm) circuit, thereby allowing for HTP automated research and decreased sample and reagent use⁴⁵. Such LOCs are widely used in the pharmaceutical industry for rapid and lower-cost drug discovery⁴⁶. Large biology labs may also include automated equipment such as solid phase extractors, DNA synthesizers, chromatographers, spectrophotometers, and imagers, in varying states of connectedness, modularity, and hands-off capabilities^{43,47}.

Higher levels of automation also typically involve greater data collection, necessitating the use of laboratory information management systems (LIMS), first introduced in the 1990s⁴⁸; increased computing power⁴⁹; and cloud computing and AI. The term “Big Data” has been used since the 1990s, though it has its roots in the early computing age of the 1960s⁵⁰ ([Big Data Framework](#), accessed 2024). The early 2000s onward saw the rise of web applications and the rapid increase in computing power and storage. With expanding databases came an advancement of ML models and techniques; these evolved from being mostly philosophical endeavors in the mid-20th century^{51–53} to data-driven ones in the 1990s with the growth of computing power. These simultaneous evolutions have made it possible for researchers of complex systems to both gather more data and create more accurate ML models. Indeed, it has now become almost essential for certain fields to embrace the era of Big Data and ever-advancing modeling capabilities to understand – and publish on – their topics. Biology is one of these complex fields, in which the more we learn, the more

difficult it becomes to design useful experiments to test and/or control for all contingencies. Manual experimentation, while good for rapid idea testing, becomes slow, tedious, and difficult at larger scales, precluding the ability of many researchers to gather enough data to build proper statistical and ML models. This is where access to increased levels of automation may become necessary – without the need to purchase large amounts of expensive equipment (Figures 3 and 4). Solutions to this dilemma include the advent of cloud labs and biofoundries, entities that take inspiration from cloud computing. Cloud computing allows users to access computing power and data storage remotely and at any time from centralized facilities that provision resources as needed. Similarly, cloud labs and biofoundries are automated, centralized spaces that allow scientists to interact with equipment, processes, and on-site laboratory facilitators through web-located application programming interfaces (APIs). Such “democratizing” of automation may allow academics and small start-ups to flexibly access the levels of automation needed at different points in their research life cycles.

This history illustrates that biology research and its automation have been coming of age together, and continue to do so; like the nearly simultaneous advent of automated PCR and DNA sequencing techniques with the birth of molecular biology, biology and automation will continue to influence each other. In addition, the integration of automation in biology is accelerating during the current age of AI maturation, presenting both unparalleled challenges and opportunities for advancement of life sciences research.

The long road to biology-ready AI

Artificial intelligence has been discussed as a possibility since Alan Turing asked the question, “Can machines think?” in his seminal 1950 paper⁵². Soon thereafter, the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence (1956) led to the establishment of AI both as a term and a discipline⁵⁴. “Inference engine” systems were built in the 1960s and 1970s at MIT (funded by DARPA) and Stanford; these early forms of AI applied logic rules to data, interpreted the data, then inferred conclusions and made predictions⁵⁵. The invention of microprocessors in the late 1970s pushed the computing and AI fields further, and the 1980s saw “expert systems” that learned how to deal with situations from human experts and then dole out advice⁵⁶. In 1997, IBM’s Deep Blue chess computer program beat the reigning world chess champion for the first time. Algorithms such as this could be termed “weak AI” or “artificial narrow intelligence” because they are based on “brute force algorithms” that “make some attempt to copy or mimic human cognitional thought,” but cannot reason or make their own decisions^{57,58}. Thus, during this period of its evolution, AI was not yet powerful or “thoughtful” enough to help biologists learn from their growing datasets, though scientists at this time began to leverage simple neural networks and ML models to understand complex processes.

The 2000s saw versions of AI and ML implemented into humanoid robots, robot vacuums, Mars rovers, social media, and driverless cars; this was driven, in part, by the rise of “Big Data” and software that could handle huge, unwieldy datasets^{59–61}. In addition, in the early-to-mid-2000s, “deep learning,” an idea that started in the 1960s and a term that was coined in the 1980s, started to make leaps and bounds in progress⁶². The deep learning method, a subset of ML, uses layers of simulated “neural networks” to try to replicate the decision-making power of the human brain⁶³: “AI is the overarching system. Machine learning is a subset of AI. Deep learning is a subfield of machine learning, and neural networks make up the backbone of deep learning algorithms”⁶⁴. Deep learning advanced upon the “nondeep,” one-to-two layered, supervised ML that requires model training on a known and labeled dataset, allowing for unsupervised learning in which the models can determine their needs from raw data alone, and then continually reevaluate their outputs^{63,65}.

The 2010s onward have seen exponential growth in ML and other AI technologies: Google X created an algorithm in 2012 that could recognize cats in videos; Facebook launched its DeepFace algorithm in 2014 that could eventually process faces with more than 97% accuracy; Google’s AlphaGO beat the world’s go game champion in 2016; Facebook trained AI chatbots to converse and learn from each other in 2017; and AI was used in 2018 to diagnose skin cancer more accurately than human doctors could^{61,66}. Much of this progress was based upon deep learning models⁶², which started outperforming other methods in ML contests in the mid-2010s⁶⁷. In addition, this deep

learning evolution has also led to recent advances in creating increasingly “strong AI” (AKA “artificial general intelligence,” AGI), as-yet-theoretical programs that are predicted be able to control a system without human intervention, perform several simultaneous tasks, and simulate “precise human cognitive or intellectual qualities, such as strong problem-solving abilities”^{58,68}. The now ubiquitous ChatGPT launched at the end of 2022; while some argue whether or not this and other large language models (LLMs) are true AGIs, they are arguably major steps toward AGI development⁶⁹. Due to advances such as these, the global AI market is predicted to grow annually by more than 20%⁷⁰.

While AI and ML have been integrated into manufacturing and chemistry automation in various forms since the start of the computer revolution of the 1960s and 1970s, the use of AI in life science experimentation is quite new. This is likely, in part, because it took the evolutionary steps listed above for AI, computing power, and data storage to advance enough to be useful for a field as complex as biology. Manufacturing and scientific disciplines such as chemistry tend to require more straightforward processes that contain fewer contingencies for AIs to parse and model. Biology, on the other hand, is highly variable (necessitating large numbers of full-factorial experiments, each with replicates); involves a huge range of scales (from molecules, to genes, to multicellular and multi-organism systems); and is comprised of large numbers of stochastic, interacting components that are hard to model^{71–73}.

Some predicted the integration of AI into the life sciences as early as 1991: because “The acquisition of data and the extraction of information from them is reaching the point at which human interception, interpretation, and intervention will no longer be possible...The field of artificial intelligence (AI) will contribute much in the future”¹. Indeed, neural networks were used as early as the 1990s to understand gene expression data⁷⁴. Yet, the Obama Administration only launched the “Big Data Research and Development Initiative” in 2012 to “transform our ability to use Big Data for scientific discovery, environmental and biomedical research, education, and national security”⁷⁵. It could be argued that, while deep learning has been used in biology since the 1990s and early 2000s, AI has not been truly ready for biology until deep learning evolved enough to handle the reams of complex data that came from inventions such as NGS. Advancements in convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) in the 2010s led to inventions such as the DeepBind algorithm from Harvard and MIT, a deep neural network that used CNNs to identify binding patterns of proteins from sequence data⁷⁶, and the AlphaFold systems for determining 3D protein structure from amino acid sequences (see below). Conversely, biology was not truly ready for AI until genetic and related sequencing technologies advanced to a point at which collecting Big Data was both possible and necessary^{58,77,78} (Figure 5).

Moving forward, AI is not only useful but may become essential for data analysis and experimental design⁷⁹: “We have massive amounts of relevant data today. But you need computational approaches, such as AI, to put it into a form that humans can understand and decide where to go next” (Daniel Ziemek of Pfizer, quoted in⁸⁰. For example, protein engineering research has benefitted from AIs assisting humans in analyzing huge databases to understand and predict protein sequences, functions, and 3D geometry and folding^{58,78}. AlphaFold2, developed by Google DeepMind (London, UK) is perhaps the most well-known and powerful of these systems, which uses AI to predict how a protein folds with an accuracy meeting or exceeding experimental methods; AlphaFold3, launched in 2024, now uses AI to predict the structure and function of

several other biomolecules, including DNA, RNA, and binding ligands⁸¹. Similarly, artificial intelligence is being used to design drugs *in silico*, predicting multiple molecular properties and selecting drug candidates for lab testing; scientists hope this will reduce the current average costs of more than \$2.5 billion and 10-15 years to develop one new drug⁸². These *in silico* predictions can then be used to run HTP automated experiments that, in turn, generate more data to inform future models. The first wholly-AI-developed drug entered Phase I clinical trials in 2022; that same drug entered Phase II trials in 2023⁸³⁻⁸⁵. And, in 2022, the FDA accepted the first AI-powered drug development tool for movement through its new qualification process⁸⁶.

Figure 5: Biology and AI are simultaneously reaching adolescence – here we show select examples through the past few decades. The foundations for both synthetic biology and AI were laid in the 1950s-1970s, with synthetic biology first experiencing the issue of increasingly large datasets in the 1970s, ‘80s, and ‘90s. The creation and use of “Big Data” in biology have grown exponentially since then, as has the power of “strong AI.” The combination of both has already resulted in novel tools and discoveries, and will likely continue to do so as the convergence of technologies matures. Note: GWAS = genome wide association study.

Biology automation in the age of AI – an unprecedented combination

Automation has been adopted by several industries, some over centuries and some over the past several decades. These have all shared commonalities as they have progressed. Each sector has worked to create machines and systems that are increasingly efficient and reliable but also flexible, and to make automation more cost effective. They have created and enforced automation standards, to varying degrees, and built and dealt with new regulations as technology has advanced. By necessity, they have developed new methods for educating and training workers under changing conditions.

The young discipline of biology automation is currently still grappling with many of these issues. However, it is also venturing into uncharted territory: life sciences labs will be some of the first automated systems to fully develop at the same time that AI is coming of age. One can only speculate how the fields will coevolve (Figure 6), though it is likely that, while disciplines such as automotive manufacturing have been very centered around tangible outputs, the biology-AI combination will likely focus to the same extent on “intangible” data production. New ideas such as “self-driving labs” (SDLs, see below), in which AI makes some-to-all of the decisions in an experimental process, did not exist when other disciplines were becoming automated. As a result, we predict that the biology-automation-AI nexus will likely optimize around the fast iteration of experiments and models to drive data output in increasingly closed-loop, self-driving systems.

Some patterns of technology emergence will likely (continue to) apply to biology automation; biology should use other industries’ experiences with automation to understand which limitations can be addressed (and how) and which cannot. For example, while *in silico* experimentation with AI will only increase, ground-truthing experiments with physical samples in physical systems will likely always be necessary due to the complexity of biology and the regulations surrounding experiments like clinical trials. Thus, biology will always be restricted to an extent by physical factors; some of these limitations will continue to be linked to physical automation itself, such as machine dimensions, robot arm movement capabilities, workflow constraints, experimental timing, and the lower limits of sample processing size (e.g., microfluidics). Biology automation must also overcome current cost restrictions in order to become truly ubiquitous. AI integration into automated processes can make them more efficient and cost-effective, but only to a certain point. Machines themselves must come down in price; while machine manufacturers may find incentives to create greater numbers of cheaper machines as biology automation becomes more implemented, this is a chicken-and-egg problem in which more scientists must adopt automation for it to become accepted, whereas automation must become more financially accessible for it to be used.

In addition, biology automation must adopt standards for

software and hardware to interplay with each other and across manufacturers; the successful adoption of standards in clinical labs/pharma and in chemistry research has contributed to the success of automation in those sectors^{87,88}. Equipment costs and standard adoptions are also intertwined, as standards allow consumers to purchase according to need rather than by availability and/or the ability to work with already-adopted technologies. Standards also allow for the interplay of data collected by different groups, particularly in conjunction with automation. Creating standardized protocols that are run in the same ways on the same automated equipment at various cloud labs and biofoundries ensures that the resulting data and metadata are compatible with those of other groups doing similar research. This, in turn, is critical for developing databases that are massive and comprehensive enough to drive useful ML models and powerful AI algorithms. The Open Datasets Initiative of Align to Innovate (Cambridge, MA) operates with a mandate to do just this: it brings together biologists, machine learning specialists, and automation experts to develop protocols for use in automated labs to collect high-fidelity, AI-ready biological datasets. Both the protocols and datasets are to be made publicly available after development so each dataset can continue to grow in standardized and robust ways⁸⁹. The current programs to create bio foundries, both in the U.S. and elsewhere, also bode well for the ability of biology automation to get past several of these current roadblocks, including high costs and lack of standards development. Though these programs are currently primarily involved in funding efforts, they will ultimately need to ensure that stakeholders across biology, automation, and computer science disciplines come together to create and agree to common standards. These programs and groups will also need to create more training for biologists coming of age in the automation and AI era, and for computer scientists and engineers who are increasingly being asked to work with biologists.

More unpredictable ways in which biology, automation, and AI will intersect lay in the realms of experimental technical difficulties and biological complexity. Some of the laboratory methods that are currently tough to automate will likely become easier as sensor technologies (e.g., cameras, motion detectors, liquid level monitors, etc.) improve and integrate AI; many of the current automation limitations surround handling and moving specimens in and from different containers and between multiple locations⁴². We will also likely see more embodiment of AI into machines in the form of (at least partial) “robot scientists” and SDLs in the near future. The definition of a SDL is still evolving, but it typically includes the involvement of AI decision-making at some point in the design-build-test-analyze-learn (DBTAL) loop; it often also includes AI control of, and/or embodiment into, automation equipment. While this is not a new idea (the first arguable robot scientists were developed in 2004 and 2009^{90,91}); the ability of AI to do “closed-

loop learning” with minimal human intervention is becoming more of a reality. While the ultimate goal of these labs may be using AI to create and execute all steps of the DBTAL process without human intervention, iterating upon hypotheses by using data generated in real time (a true “robot scientist”), current SDLs leverage AI decision-making in portions of the experimental cycle to augment human capabilities. An SDL may be currently as simple as one using AI to interpret regular and simple processes (e.g., identifying process issues and anomalies so human operators can fix them); it may use humans to develop experimental protocols and goals with the AI acting as an assistant that does simple data analysis; or it may be capable of acting as an experimental “manager” with a human “assistant” who only sets initial experimental goals and then receives results. The latter is, at present, possible in some chemistry and material science labs for well-defined processes⁴³; life sciences experiments are currently still too complex to allow for full AI integration beyond the simpler levels. The benefits and drawbacks of using SDLs and robot scientists are still being explored as they develop in real time. While these capabilities will likely improve in the future, we may always desire human input in science, if for no other reason

than the fact that fortuitous discoveries – the “happy accidents” of science – may happen even less with more well-controlled, non-human scientists.

Some biology methods, of course, may ultimately have chemical and physical limitations that cannot be overcome with AI solutions. While fully autonomous, AI-driven robotic labs may be more difficult to achieve in biology because of these issues, some suggest that a hybrid approach may allow for powerful results. For example, Martin et al.⁴³ have explained that, “Current technical limitations limit our ability to automate all experiments, so SDLs should be able to produce unequivocal instructions for humans to follow in traditional labs, and ingest the data so produced.” In addition, they “envisage that a SDL would store its accumulating knowledge as a digital twin, whose role evolves as more is learned about the biological system it is analyzing.” Digital twins are virtual replicas of real-world objects or systems, models that are updated with real-time data to make decisions about and improve upon the original physical entity. These forms of ML models/AI can run many simulations at once to study multiple and/or complex processes while in constant dialog with their physical systems, allowing them to study more complicated entities than can regular simulations⁹².

Figure 6: Biology and AI are reaching adolescence simultaneously, creating previously-unseen opportunities. Manufacturing, along with automation of its processes, has occurred for several centuries (millennia if one counts the use of waterwheels and windmills). Semiconductor manufacturing was able to almost immediately use the advances in automation created for other facilities making tangible goods. The pharmaceutical industry started long before experimental, evidence-based biology; many of the companies that would go on to develop drugs and clinical devices began as chemical manufacturing factories for products such as dyes and were thus able to begin using manufacturing-based automation early in their existence. Biology, particularly synthetic biology, with its requirements for handling micro-scale samples generating more and more complex data, has its roots in early microbiology of the late 1800s, but really began with the discovery of DNA in the mid-1900s. While biology has been able to incorporate some automation technology from other disciplines (such as chemistry), the rise of more ubiquitous molecular biology experimentation in the late 20th and early 21st centuries has coincided with the advent of automated equipment and processes specifically designed for biology. This positive feedback between biology and its automation technologies is also now taking place as AI rapidly matures. The creation of tangible goods can be optimized only to a certain degree with the use of AI, as they are, by their very nature, constrained by physicalities. Biology, however (as well as modern pharma research) is becoming increasingly data-driven, providing an unprecedented use-case for increasingly powerful AI technology to be incorporated into the biology-automation virtuous cycle.

Conclusion

Automation has been adopted by various disciplines many times throughout human history. The full integration of automation into life sciences research will likely follow a somewhat similar trajectory, going through many of the same growing pains, as it has in the past. However, the present marks the first time that we are working to automate a discipline while AI is becoming useful and powerful. Thus, while there are expected impediments to automating biology experimentation, AI will likely help the discipline not only to solve these problems but to accelerate biology research in unforeseen ways. Artificial intelligence can improve both automated machines/processes and the understanding of the data that results from these high-throughput experiments, essential for the nearly unbound nature of biological questions. In turn, biology is a field that almost begs for the use of AI and automation in its experiments; biological systems contain

such a multitude of details and interactions that studying them requires high-throughput experimentation, resulting in more data than any human can understand. The ability of AI models to parse these data will only improve, essential in a sector that requires analyses beyond the straightforward equations used in physics and chemistry. And, while the adoption of automation in biology requires that scientists become technology “experts,” we find ourselves at a unique moment – for the first time in the history of automation, AI can help bridge the gap between “wet lab” and “dry lab” knowledge, allowing people to become “amphibious researchers”⁹³ in automated labs with just a few requests from an AI. Thus, while we can follow the lines of history to understand the path toward integrating automation and biology, we also find ourselves looking into the unknown as two young disciplines – biology automation and AI – come of age together.

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References

1. Beugelsdijk, T. J. The future of laboratory automation. *Genet. Anal. Tech. Appl.* **8**, 217–220 (1991).
2. Joshi, S. H., Green, E. R. & Rogers, K. biology. *Encyclopedia Britannica* (2024).
3. Opal, S. M. A brief history of microbiology and immunology. in *Vaccines: A Biography* 31–56 (Springer New York, New York, NY, 2009).
4. Kaufmann, S. H. E. & Winau, F. From bacteriology to immunology: the dualism of specificity. *Nat. Immunol.* **6**, 1063–1066 (2005).
5. Gayon, J. From Mendel to epigenetics: History of genetics. *C. R. Biol.* **339**, 225–230 (2016).
6. Beadle, G. W. & Tatum, E. L. Genetic control of biochemical reactions in *Neurospora*. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **27**, 499–506 (1941).
7. Horowitz, N. H. The one gene-one enzyme hypothesis. *Genetics* **33**, 612 (1948).
8. Jackson, D. A., Symons, R. H. & Berg, P. Biochemical method for inserting new genetic information into DNA of simian virus 40: Circular SV40 DNA molecules containing lambda phage genes and the galactose operon of *Escherichia coli*. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **69**, 2904–2909 (1972).
9. Olsen, K. The first 110 years of laboratory automation: Technologies, applications, and the creative scientist. *SLAS Technol.* **17**, 469–480 (2012).
10. Shakespear, G. & Weaver, E. Notes and correspondence: Automatic methods of gas analysis depending upon thermal conductivity. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* **12**, 1027–1028 (1920).
11. Balch, R. T. & Paine, H. S. Factory operation of automatic electrometric pH control of cane juice defecation. *Ind. Eng. Chem.* **20**, 348–353 (1928).
12. Somerville, A. A., Ball, J. M. & Edland, L. A. Autographic stress-strain curves of rubber at low elongations. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.* **2**, 289–293 (1930).
13. Ferguson, B., Jr. Semiautomatic fractionation. A rapid analytical method. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.* **14**, 493–496 (1942).
14. Olsen, K. K. Rosie the robot, laboratory automation and the second world war, 1941 to 1945. *Lab. Robot. Autom.* **9**, 105–112 (1997).
15. Lingane, J. J. Automatic potentiometric titrations. *Anal. Chem.* **20**, 285–292 (1948).
16. Martin, S. M. Automatic starter for chromatograms. *Anal. Chem.* **30**, 1890–1890 (1958).
17. Van Duuren, B. L. Automatic solvent addition funnel for paper chromatography. *Anal. Chem.* **32**, 732–733 (1960).
18. Mullen, P. W. & Anton, A. Multifunction automatic recording photometric titrator. *Anal. Chem.* **32**, 103–106 (1960).
19. The history of automated liquid handling. *LabAutopedia* <https://diyhpl.us/~bryan/irc/labautopedia-history-of-automated-liquid-handling.html>.
20. Microlit. What is the history of micropipettes? *Microlit* <https://www.microlit.us/what-is-the-history-of-micropipettes/> (2022).
21. Zinnen, T. The micropipette story. *Outreach* <https://outreach.biotech.wisc.edu/the-micropipette-story/> (2004).
22. No more sucking: 60 years of the micropipete. *Biomedical Scientist* <https://thebiomedicalscientist.net/2017/07/24/no-more-sucking-60-years-micropipette/> (2024).
23. Bogue, R. Robots in the laboratory: a review of applications. *Ind. Rob.* **39**, 113–119 (2012).
24. Tecan Company History. *Tecan* <https://www.tecan.com/history>.
25. McClymont, D. W. & Freemont, P. S. With all due respect to Maholo, lab automation isn't anthropomorphic. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **35**, 312–314 (2017).
26. Bessman, M. J., Lehman, I. R., Simms, E. S. & Kornberg, A. Enzymatic synthesis of deoxyribonucleic acid. *J. Biol. Chem.* **233**, 171–177 (1958).
27. Brock, T. D. & Freeze, H. *Thermus aquaticus* gen. n. and sp. n., a Nonsporulating Extreme Thermophile. *J. Bacteriol.* **98**, 289–297 (1969).
28. Mullis, K. et al. Specific enzymatic amplification of DNA in vitro: The polymerase chain reaction. *Cold Spring Harb. Symp. Quant. Biol.* **51**, 263–273 (1986).
29. Zhu, H. et al. PCR past, present and future. *Biotechniques* **69**, 317–325 (2020).
30. Smithsonian Institution Archives. Record unit 9577 history of the polymerase chain reaction videohistory collection, 1992-1993. (2011).
31. Cheriyaedath, S. History of polymerase chain reaction (PCR). *News-Medical* [https://www.news-medical.net/life-sciences/History-of-Polymerase-Chain-Reaction-\(PCR\).aspx](https://www.news-medical.net/life-sciences/History-of-Polymerase-Chain-Reaction-(PCR).aspx) (2016).
32. Sanger, F., Nicklen, S. & Coulson, A. R. DNA sequencing with chain-terminating inhibitors. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **74**, 5463–5467 (1977).
33. Schroeder, K. A history of sequencing. *Front Line Genomics* <https://frontlinegenomics.com/a-history-of-sequencing/> (2022).
34. Applied Biosystems Inc. Prototype Automated DNA Gene Sequencer.
35. Ronaghi, M., Karamohamed, S., Pettersson, B., Uhlén, M. & Nyren, P. Real-time DNA sequencing using detection of pyrophosphate release. *Anal. Biochem.* **242**, 84–89 (1996).

36. Heather, J. M. & Chain, B. The sequence of sequencers: The history of sequencing DNA. *Genomics* **107**, 1–8 (2016).
37. Margulies, M. et al. Genome sequencing in microfabricated high-density picolitre reactors. *Nature* **437**, 376–380 (2005).
38. Liu, L. et al. Comparison of next-generation sequencing systems. *J. Biomed. Biotechnol.* **2012**, 1–11 (2012).
39. Chao, R., Mishra, S., Si, T. & Zhao, H. Engineering biological systems using automated biofoundries. *Metab. Eng.* **42**, 98–108 (2017).
40. Holland, I. & Davies, J. A. Automation in the life science research laboratory. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **8**, 571777 (2020).
41. Zielinski, D., Gordon, A., Zaks, B. L. & Erlich, Y. iPipet: sample handling using a tablet. *Nat. Methods* **11**, 784–785 (2014).
42. Blackburn, T. No shortcuts to the lab of the future. *Emerald Cloud Lab* <https://blog.emeraldcloudlab.com/no-shortcuts-to-the-lab-of-the-future/> (2021).
43. Martin, H. G. et al. Perspectives for self-driving labs in synthetic biology. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **79**, 102881 (2023).
44. Hansen, A. D. A., Pollard, M. J., Searles, W. L., Uber, D. C. & Jaklevic, J. M. *A High-Speed Automated Colony Picking Machine*. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/83t9n2n1> (1993).
45. Meldrum, D. Automation for genomics, part two: Sequencers, microarrays, and future trends. *Genome Res.* **10**, 1288–1303 (2000).
46. Ma, C., Peng, Y., Li, H. & Chen, W. Organ-on-a-chip: A new paradigm for drug development. *Trends Pharmacol. Sci.* **42**, 119–133 (2021).
47. Scientific Instrumentation. *Emerald Cloud Lab* <https://www.emeraldcloudlab.com/instrumentation/>.
48. Timeline of Life Science and Lab Automation Innovations: What's Next? *Monterey Automation* <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/timeline-life-science-lab-automation-innovations/> (2023).
49. Slezak, T. Computers & biology: The early years. *LinkedIn* <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/computers-biology-early-years-tom-slezak/> (2018).
50. A short history of Big Data. *Enterprise Big Data Framework* <https://www.bigdataframework.org/knowledge/a-short-history-of-big-data/> (2021).
51. McCulloch, W. S. & Pitts, W. A logical calculus of the ideas immanent in nervous activity. *Bulletin of Mathematical Biophysics* **5**, 115–133 (1943).
52. Turing, A. M. I.—computing machinery and intelligence. *Mind* **LIX**, 433–460 (1950).
53. Samuel, A. L. Some studies in machine learning using the game of checkers. *IBM J. Res. Dev.* **44**, 206–226 (2000).
54. Dick, S. Artificial Intelligence. *Harvard Data Science Review* (2019).
55. What is an inference engine in machine learning? *run.ai* <https://www.run.ai/guides/machine-learning-inference/inference-engine>.
56. Anyoha, R. The history of artificial intelligence. *Science in the News* <https://sitn.hms.harvard.edu/flash/2017/history-artificial-intelligence/> (2017).
57. Fjelland, R. Why general artificial intelligence will not be realized. *Humanit. Soc. Sci. Commun.* **7**, 1–9 (2020).
58. Bhardwaj, A., Kishore, S. & Pandey, D. K. Artificial intelligence in biological sciences. *Life (Basel)* **12**, 1430 (2022).
59. Firican, G. The history of big data. *LightsOnData* <https://www.lightsondata.com/the-history-of-big-data/> (2022).
60. Reynoso, R. Brief history of artificial intelligence - from 1900 till now. *G2* <https://www.g2.com/articles/history-of-artificial-intelligence> (2024).
61. What is the history of artificial intelligence (AI)? *Tableau from Salesforce* <https://www.tableau.com/data-insights/ai/history>.
62. Bengio, Y. Springtime for AI: The rise of deep learning. *Scientific American* (2016).
63. Jim Holdsworth, M. S. What is deep learning? *IBM* <https://www.ibm.com/topics/deep-learning> (2024) doi:10.1201/9781003339175-12.
64. AI vs. Machine learning vs. Deep learning vs. Neural networks. *IBM* <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/ai-vs-machine-learning-vs-deep-learning-vs-neural-networks> (2024).
65. China, C. R. Types of machine learning. *IBM* <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/machine-learning-types> (2024).
66. Pitchford, D. A decade of advancements as we enter A new age of AI. *Forbes* (2019).
67. Schmidhuber, J. Deep learning in neural networks: An overview. *arXiv [cs.NE]* (2014).
68. Chakriswaran, P. et al. Emotion AI-driven sentiment analysis: A survey, future research directions, and open issues. *Appl. Sci. (Basel)* **9**, 5462 (2019).
69. Knight, W. Some glimpse AGI in ChatGPT. Others call it a mirage. *Wired* (2023).
70. Artificial Intelligence - Worldwide. <https://www.statista.com/outlook/tmo/artificial-intelligence/worldwide> (2024).
71. McLaughlin, J. A. et al. The synthetic biology open language (SBOL) version 3: Simplified data exchange for bioengineering. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **8**, (2020).
72. Leins, D. A., Haase, S. B., Eslami, M., Schrier, J. & Freeman, J. T. Collaborative methods to enhance reproducibility and accelerate discovery. *Digit. Discov.* **2**, 12–27 (2023).

73. Synergistic Discovery and Design (SD2) (Archived). *DARPA Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency* <https://www.darpa.mil/program/synergistic-discovery-and-design>.
74. Kumar, S. et al. Deep learning in computational biology: Advancements, challenges, and future outlook. *arXiv [cs.LG]* (2023).
75. PRESS RELEASE: Obama administration unveils 'big data' initiative: Announces \$200 million in new R&D investments. *The White House* (2012).
76. Alipanahi, B., DeLong, A., Weirauch, M. T. & Frey, B. J. Predicting the sequence specificities of DNA- and RNA-binding proteins by deep learning. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **33**, 831–838 (2015).
77. Pettersson, E., Lundeberg, J. & Ahmadian, A. Generations of sequencing technologies. *Genomics* **93**, 105–111 (2009).
78. Chakraborty, I., Choudhury, A. & Banerjee, T. S. Artificial intelligence in biological data. *Journal of Information Technology & Software Engineering* **7**, 1000207–1000207 (2017).
79. Han, H. & Liu, W. The coming era of artificial intelligence in biological data science. *BMC Bioinformatics* **20**, (2019).
80. Fujimori, S. When AI meets biology. *Pfizer* <https://www.pfizer.com/news/behind-the-science/when-ai-meets-biology> (7/2022).
81. AlphaFold. *Google DeepMind* <https://deepmind.google/technologies/alphafold/>.
82. Dara, S., Dhamecherla, S., Jadav, S. S., Babu, C. H. M. & Ahsan, M. J. Machine learning in drug discovery: A review. *Artif. Intell. Rev.* **55**, 1947–1999 (2022).
83. Chace, C. First wholly AI-developed drug enters Phase 1 trials. *Forbes* (2022).
84. Insilico Medicine. First drug discovered and designed with generative AI enters Phase II trials, with first patients dosed. *PR Newswire* (2023).
85. Insilico Medicine. Insilico: linking target discovery and generative chemistry AI platforms for a drug discovery breakthrough. *Springer Nature* <https://www.nature.com/articles/d43747-021-00039-5>.
86. Park, A. FDA accepts first AI algorithm to drug development tool pilot, with Deliberate AI's anxiety and depression assessment. *Fierce Biotech* (2024).
87. Kingston, H. M. Consortium on Automated Analytical Laboratory Systems (CAALS). *Journal of Automated Methods and Management in Chemistry* **12**, 113–115 (1990).
88. Boyd, J. Robotic laboratory automation. *Science* **295**, 517–518 (2002).
89. The Datasets. *Align to Innovate* <https://alignbio.org/datasets-program>.
90. King, R. D. et al. Functional genomic hypothesis generation and experimentation by a robot scientist. *Nature* **427**, 247–252 (2004).
91. King, R. D. et al. The automation of science. *Science* **324**, 85–89 (2009).
92. What is a digital twin? *IBM* <https://www.ibm.com/topics/what-is-a-digital-twin> (2021).
93. Mellingwood, C. R. Amphibious researchers: working with laboratory automation in synthetic biology. (The University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, Scotland, 2019).